

Eudesmane derivatives from some Asteraceae plants – An overview[†]

Vivek Krishna^a, Poonam Khandelwal^b, Neetu Koolwal^c, M. C. Sharma^c and Pahup Singh*^c

^aEmcure Pharmaceutical Ltd., Plot No. 2, ITBT Park, MIDC Hinjwadi, Pune-411 057, Maharashtra, India

^bDepartment of Chemistry, Mohanlal Sukhadia University, Udaipur-313 001, Rajasthan, India

^cDepartment of Chemistry, University of Rajasthan, Jaipur-302 004, Rajasthan, India

E-mail : pahupsingh@yahoo.co.uk

Manuscript received 17 January 2014, accepted 30 March 2014

Abstract : The chemistry of *epi-ilicic acid* from the aerial parts of *Alcantara ekmaniana*, **1 β -hydroxy-3 α -isobutyryloxy** and **1 β -hydroxy-3 α -[2-methylbutyryloxy]-arbusculin A** from the aerial parts of *Bishopanthus soliceps*, **11 α ,13-dihydrotubiferin** from the roots of *Dicoma anomala* and eighteen eudesmanolides from the aerial parts of *Dimerostemma brasilianum* have been briefly reviewed.

Keywords : *Epi-ilicic acid*, eudesmanolides, *Alcantara ekmaniana*, *Bishopanthus soliceps*, *Dicoma anomala*, *D. schinzii*, *Dimerostemma brasilianum*, Asteraceae.

Introduction

Eudesmane (**I**), a bicyclic sesquiterpene with two methyls and an isopropyl group is biogenetically derived from *trans, trans* farnesyl pyrophosphate¹, which on subsequent oxidative modification and cyclization gives eudesmanolides. Thus lactones derived from eudesmane skeleton are called eudesmanolides. Most of them are γ -

lactones and their formation probably involves oxidation of one of the two methyl groups in the isopropyl 'head' of acyclic farnesol precursor to a carboxylic group, oxidation of an adjacent methylene group to a secondary alcohol function and eventual intramolecular ring closure lead to the formation of eudesmanolides. The details of this reaction are not known.

Lactones seem to be characteristic metabolites of the family Asteraceae. The α -methylene- γ -lactones are either *cis* or *trans* fused to the C₆-C₇ or C₈-C₇ positions of the carbocyclic skeleton. The major types of lactones resulting from enzyme mediated cyclizations are classified primarily on the basis of their carbocyclic skeleton. These lactones are colourless, bitter, relatively stable, lipophilic constituents and their nature varies from colourless oil to

[†]In honour of Professor K. C. Joshi on the occasion of his 88th birthday.

Thus the only difference between methyl ester of ilicic acid **4b** and **5b** was the stereochemistry at C-4. The detailed assignment of various absorptions of compounds **4b**, **5b** and **6** are shown in Table 2.

Table 2. ^1H NMR spectral data (δ , ppm) of compounds **4b**, **5b** and **6** (400 MHz, CDCl_3 , TMS as internal standard)

H	4b	5b	6
5-H	1.93 brd	1.85 brd	1.65 brd
7-H	2.53 dddd	2.53 dddd	1.80 dddd
13-H	6.14 brs	6.15 brs	2.15 ddd
13'-H	5.56 brs	5.58 brs	1.60 ddd
14-H	0.92 s	1.06 s	0.98 s
15-H	1.12 s	1.15 s	1.14 s
16-H	–	–	4.60 ddd
16'-H	–	–	4.53 ddd
O-Me	3.77 s	3.76 s	3.78 s

J (Hz) : $5\alpha,6\beta = 12$; $6\alpha,7\alpha = 4$; $6\beta,7\alpha = 12$; $7\alpha,8\alpha = 4$; $7\alpha,8\beta = 12$; compound **6** : $13,13' = 15$; $13,16 = 5$; $13,16' = 9$; $13',16' = 9$; $16,16' = 18$.

No work has been done on any part of the new monotypic genus *Bishopanthus* (Asteraceae, tribe Liabeae)¹¹. The aerial parts of *B. soliceps* H. Robins afforded 1β -hydroxy- 3α -isobutyryloxy arbusculin A **7** and 1β -hydroxy- 3α -[2-methylbutyryloxy]-arbusculin A **8** in addition to highly oxygenated guaianolides⁴.

The ^1H NMR spectral data of **7** and **8** (Table 3) exhibited same similarities to that of 1β -hydroxyarbusculin A¹². However, a double doublet at 5.03 ppm and the additional signals of ester groups indicated the presence of an

oxygen function at C-3 whereas the coupling required an α -orientation. Spin decoupling supported this assumption and noes of both H-14 and H-15 with H-6 led to the assignment of the configuration shown. The nature of the ester groups followed from the typical signals and the presence of acylium ions at m/z 71 ($\text{C}_3\text{H}_7\text{CO}^+$) and 85 ($\text{C}_4\text{H}_9\text{CO}^+$) respectively in the mass spectra.

Chemical investigations of the two species of genus *Dicoma* (Asteraceae, tribe Mutisieae) have shown that 14,15-oxygenated germacranolides are present^{13,14}. Re-investigation of the roots of *Dicoma anomala* Sond. subsp. *cirsioides* (Harv.) Willd. gave eudesmanolides **9**¹⁵, **10**, **11**¹⁶ along with germacranolides and guaianolides while the roots of *Dicoma schinzii* O. Hoffm. afforded eudesmanolides **9**¹⁵, **11**¹⁶ and **12**¹⁶.

The structure of **10** clearly deduced from the ^1H NMR spectrum (Table 3), especially when it was compared with those of **9** and **12**. Some signals, however, were different from those of **12**¹⁶. The β -orientation of the 11-methyl group established from the observed coupling $J_{7,11}$ and **10** was named as $11\alpha,\beta$ -dihydrotubiferin.

Table 3. ^1H NMR spectral data (δ , ppm) of compounds **7**, **8** and **10** (400 MHz, CDCl_3 , TMS) as internal standard

H	7	8	10
1-H	3.79 dd	3.79 dd	6.69 d
2-H	1.93 m	1.93 m	5.90 d
3-H	5.03 dd	5.03 dd	–
4-H	–	–	2.58 dq
5-H	2.16 d	2.16 d	2.08 dd
6-H	4.15 dd	4.15 dd	4.21 dd
7-H	2.65 m	2.65 m	2.12 ddd
8 α -H	2.10 m	2.10 m	1.60 m
8 β -H	1.60 dddd	1.60 dddd	1.68 ddd
9 α -H	2.07 m	2.07 m	1.77 m
9 β -H	1.40 m	1.40 m	–
11-H	–	–	2.64 dq
13-H	6.13 d	6.13 d	1.22 d
13'-H	5.46 d	5.46 d	–
14-H	1.00 s	1.00 s	1.18 s
15-H	1.39 s	1.39 s	1.37 s
OCOCHMe ₂	2.62 qq	–	–
	1.18 d	–	–
	1.19 d	–	–
OCOCH(Me)CH ₂ CH ₃	–	2.53 tq	–
	–	0.91 t	–
	–	1.16 d	–

J (Hz) : Compounds **7** and **8** : 1 α ,2 α = 5; 1 α ,2 β = 11; 2 α ,2 β = 3; 5,6 = 6,7 = 11; 7,13 = 3.5; 7,13' = 3; compound **10** : 1,2 = 10; 4,5 = 11; 4,15 = 7.5; 5,6 = 6,7 = 10.5; 7,8 α = 4; 7,8 β = 10; 7,11 = 7; 8 α ,8 β = 13; 8 β ,9 α = 10; 8 β ,9 β = 4; iBu : 2,3 = 2,4 = 7; 2Mebu : 2,3 = 2,5 = 3,4 = 7.

Previously two species *Dimerostemma lippioides*¹⁷ and *D. asperatum*¹⁸ of the genus *Dimerostemma* (Asteraceae, subtribe Verbesininae) have been investigated chemically and both contained typical eudesmanolides. The substitution pattern was identical in all compounds. The aerial parts of *Dimerostemma brasilianum* Cass. on investigation gave eudesmanolides **13**¹⁹, **14**¹⁹, **21**¹⁸, **22**¹⁹ and **35**²⁰ as well as eighteen further eudesmanolides, which were difficult to separate. Besides the epoxides **13** and **14**, six similar lactones were isolated, all with the same substitution pattern. Lactone **15** was identical with the acetate obtained by partial acetylation of **14**¹⁹. The ^1H NMR spectral data of **16** (Table 4) exhibited that the ester group at C-1 was 4'-acetoxyangelate, while that of **17** was tiglate, that of **18** was methacrylate, that of **19** was epoxybutyrate and that of **20** was hydroxymethacrylate.

Consequently, the ^1H NMR spectral data of **16-20** were nearly identical with those of **13** and **14**¹⁹.

The ^1H NMR spectral data of compounds **23-28** (Table 5) were close to those of **22**¹⁹, the ^1H NMR spectrum of which differed from that of **14** in the chemical shifts of H-15 and the missing W-coupling $J_{3,15}$. Various ester residues were characterized from their characteristic ^1H NMR signals.

Table 4. ¹H NMR spectral data (δ, ppm) of compounds **16-20** (400 MHz, CDCl₃, TMS as internal standard)

H	16	17	18	19	20
1-H	4.85 dd	4.85 dd	4.82 dd	4.78 dd	4.86 dd
5-H	2.38 d	2.38 d	2.42 d	2.36 d	2.41 d
6-H	3.85 dd	3.85 dd	3.86 dd	3.85 dd	3.86 dd
7-H	2.53 dddd	2.53 dddd	2.54 dddd	2.52 dddd	2.53 dddd
8-H	3.99 ddd	3.99 ddd	3.98 ddd	3.98 ddd	3.98 ddd
13-H	6.15 d	6.18 d	6.15 dd	6.16 d	6.16 dd
13'-H	5.97 d	5.99 d	5.97 brd	5.97 d	5.97 d
14-H	1.10 s	1.10 s	1.10 s	1.10 s	1.10 s
15-H	3.22 dd	3.22 dd	3.22 dd	3.20 dd	3.22 dd
15'-H	2.90 d	2.90 d	2.90 d	2.90 d	2.90 d
OCOR	6.12 ddq 5.05 ddq 5.10 ddq 2.04 ddt 2.13 s	6.80 qq 1.97 dq 1.95 dq	6.21 brs 5.67 dq 2.02 dd	3.16 d 2.85 d 1.64 s	6.37 brs 5.97 brs 4.40 brs

J (Hz) : 1,2 = 1,2' = 2.7; 3,15 = 1.5; 5,6 = 6,7 = 10; 7,8 = 11; 7,13 = 3.5; 7,13' = 3; 8,9 α = 11; 8,9 β = 4.5; 15,15' = 3.5 (compounds **18** and **19** : 13,13' = 0.7); 5-acetoxy ang : 3',4' = 5; 3',5' = 1.5; 4',4' = 17; 4',5' = 1.5; Tigl : 3',4' = 7; 3',5' = 4',5' = 1.3; Meacr : 3',4' = 1.3; 4',4 = 1; epoxybutyrate : 3,3' = 6.

Though the relative positions of the ester groups in **23-25** could not be established with certainty. Identical chemical shifts of H-1 strongly suggested that the unsaturated ester group was at C-1 in all cases.

The ¹H NMR spectra of **29** and **30** (Table 6) which could not be separated, showed that these lactones differed only in the nature of the ester group, but contained an additional hydroxy group. Spin decoupling showed

that this group had to be placed at C-3, while the stereochemistry arrived from the coupling observed.

While **31** and **32** could not be separated but **33** was obtained pure. The ^1H NMR spectral data (Table 6) of

the mixture of **31** and **32** clearly showed that these compounds differed only in the nature of the ester group at C-

1. Remaining signals H-1 to H-15 were nearly the same.

Only a few signals differed slightly. Their assignments

Table 5. ^1H NMR spectral data (δ , ppm) of compounds **23-28** (400 MHz, CDCl_3 , TMS as internal standard)

H	23	24	25	26	27	28
1-H	4.86 brdd	4.86 brdd	4.86 brdd	4.90 brdd	4.84 brdd	4.89 brdd
5-H	2.60 d	2.60 d	2.60 d	2.54 d	2.57 d	2.57 d
6-H	3.92 dd	3.92 dd	3.92 dd	3.83 dd	3.85 dd	3.84 dd
7-H	2.76 dddd	2.76 dddd	2.76 dddd	2.52 dddd	2.53 dddd	2.53 dddd
8-H	5.22 ddd	5.22 ddd	5.20 ddd	4.11 ddd	4.15 ddd	4.10 ddd
13-H	6.12 d	6.12 d	6.12 d	6.15 d	6.16 d	6.15 d
13'-H	5.54 d	5.54 d	5.52 d	5.99 d	5.97 d	5.97 d
14-H	1.28 s	1.28 s	1.28 s	1.22 s	1.22 s	1.22 s
15-H	3.42 d	3.42 d	3.42 d	3.42 d	3.43 d	3.42 d
15'-H	2.45 d	2.45 d	2.44 d	2.42 d	2.44 d	2.44 d
OCOR	6.32 brs	6.32 brs	6.32 br	6.03 ddq	6.80 tq	6.32 brs
	5.95 brs	5.95 brs	5.94 brs	5.00 ddq	4.78 dq	5.92 brs
	4.40 brs	4.40 brs	4.40 brs	5.10 ddq	1.95 dt	4.39 brs
	2.25 brd	2.37 tq	2.57 qq	2.01 dt	2.12 s	-
	2.16 m	1.68 ddq	1.19 d	2.09 s	-	-
	0.97 d	0.92 t	1.18 d	-	-	-
	-	1.15 d	-	-	-	-

J (Hz) : 1,2 = 1,2' ~ 2.5; 5,6 = 6,7 = 7,8 = 11; 7,13 = 3.3; 7,13' = 3.0; 8,9 α = 11; 8,9 β = 4.5; 15,15' = 4.3; iVal : 2',3' = 4',5' = 7; 2Mebu : 2',3', = 2',5' = 3',4' = 7; 3',3' = 14; iBu : 2',3' = 2',4' = 7; 4'-acetoxy ang : 3,3' = 17; 3',4' = 5; 3',5' = 4',5' = 1.5; 4'-acetoxy tigl : 3',4' = 6; 3',5' = 4',5' = 1.

Table 6. ^1H NMR spectral data (δ , ppm) of compounds **29-34** (400 MHz, CDCl_3 , TMS as internal standard)

H	29	30	31	32	33	34
1-H	-	4.94 dd	-	4.66 brs	4.71 brs	4.77 brd
2-H	-	{ 2.33 m 1.97 m	-	4.01 brs	4.02 brs	{ 2.47 brd 1.9 m
3-H	-	4.17 dd	-	5.53 brs	5.53 brs	5.34 brs
5-H	-	2.36 d	-	2.68 brd	2.67 brd	2.73 brd
6-H	-	3.93 dd	-	4.00 dd	4.00 dd	3.98 dd
7-H	-	2.54 dddd	-	2.58 dddd	2.58 dddd	2.57 dddd
8-H	-	4.00 ddd	4.23 ddd	4.22 ddd	4.21 ddd	4.17 ddd
13-H	-	6.16 d	-	6.19 d	6.19 d	6.18 d
13'-H	-	5.97 d	-	5.99 d	5.99 d	5.98 d
14-H	1.11 s	1.12 s	1.11 s	1.10 s	1.10 s	0.97 s
15-H	-	3.39 d	-	1.96 brs	1.97 brs	1.90 brs
15'-H	-	3.15 d	-	-	-	-
OCOR	6.18 brs	6.13 qq	6.12 brs	6.86 qq	6.27 brs	6.25 brs
	5.68 dq	1.89 dq	5.63 dq	1.85 dq	5.92 brs	5.88 brs
	2.00 dd	1.85 dq	1.96 brs	1.83 dq	4.36 brs	4.35 brs

J (Hz) : compounds **29** and **30** : 1,2 = 1,2' = 3; 2,3 = 12; 2',3 = 5; 5,6 = 6,7 = 7,8 = 10; 7,13 = 3; 15,15' = 4; compounds **31** and **32** : 1,2 ~ 3; 5,6 = 6,7 = 7,8 = 11; 8,9 α = 11; 8,9 β = 5; 7,13 = 3; compound **33** : 5,6 = 6,7 = 10; 7,8 = 8,9 α = 11; 8,9 β = 4.5; 7,13 = 3; compound **34** : 1,2 = 4.5; 2,2' = 17; 5,6 = 6,7 = 7,8 = 11; 7,13 = 3; 8,9 α = 11; 8,9 β = 4; Meacr : 3',4' = 4',4' ~ 1; Tigl : 3',4' = 7; 3',5' = 4',5' = 1.5.

were possible, due to the different proportions of **31** and **32** in the mixture. The ^1H NMR spectral data of **33** differed from **34** only by an additional hydroxyl group, which had to be placed at C-2, as the corresponding proton showed a coupling with that at C-1. The stereochemistry followed from the small coupling $J_{2,3}$.

The ^1H NMR spectrum of **34** (Table 6) was in part similar to that of **28**. However, the signals of the epoxy protons were replaced by the signal of an olefinic methyl. An additional olefinic proton displayed a broadened singlet at 5.34 ppm, which was coupled with the olefinic methyl group thus establishing the position of the double bond. All other signals were in agreement with the proposed structures. It was named as dimerostemmabراسiolide-1-0-(3-hydroxymethyl).

So far the constituents of *Dimerostemma* show a very uniform picture, epoxidized eudesmanolides being typical. From *Zexmenia phyllocephala*^{19,20} and from a *Podanthus* species²¹, both belonging to the same subtribe, similar lactones without the epoxide grouping were isolated.

In conclusion, this short review narrated the work done in Technical University, Berlin, in Germany during the stay of PS under AVH fellowship programme.

Acknowledgement

The authors gratefully acknowledge the financial support from UGC, New Delhi for Emeritus Scientistship to PS (Grant No. 40-68/(SR) dated 5.7.2011).

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